

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

RESEARCH COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT MODEL OF THE ACADEMIC STAFF IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract

The paper deals with the issue of assessing the research competence of the academic staff in higher educational institutions. The criteria for carrying out an objective analysis of the state of research competence formation of the academic staff are described. Indicators that reveal the main features of the above mentioned criteria and imply the possibility of assessment using appropriate techniques, questionnaires, tests, etc. are defined.

Keywords: structural and functional model, research competence, academic staff, higher educational institutions.

According to the modern European education paradigm, the formation of a competent personality is nowadays in the focus of educational activity. Taking into account the current and future impact of information technologies on all the spheres of human life, and in particular on scientific and professional activity, we consider it necessary to work out a model for the research competence development of the scientific staff of higher educational institutions.

Theoretical substantiation and construction of models for the research competence development of the academic staff of higher educational institutions are presented in the works of M. Arkhypova [1], N. Bondarenko [2], M. Vinnyk [3], M. Golovan [4], G. Kovtun [5], N. Osypova [6] and others.

Modeling is a general scientific and theoretical research method, when not only the object of knowledge itself is studied, but also its reflection in the form of a model, whereas the research result is transferred from the model to the object. A model is an object that corresponds to another object, replaces it in cognition and provides information about it or a part of it. Visual modeling takes place on the basis of the researcher's ideas about the real object by creating a visual model that reproduces the phenomena and processes that occur in the object [7, p. 79].

We consider the research competence development model of the academic staff as the schematic and descriptive characteristics of the author's system of process organization, which contains the following structural components: purpose, principles, stages of research competence development, its approaches and levels, as well as pedagogical conditions, forms, methods and means, diagnostics through criteria and result.

Accordingly, the presented model consists of four interconnected and mutually determined blocks: target (goal), methodical (principles, scientific approaches), content-procedural (pedagogical conditions of research

competence, structural components of research competence, stages of research competence development, methods, forms, tools etc), diagnostic-corrective (analytical summary of the result achieved).

The target component of the model is represented by a goal, which achievement requires the implementation of the following tasks: 1) strengthening the motivation of the academic staff for scientific research activities and development of relevant value orientations; 2) formation of a theoretical knowledge system about research activity, application of these skills into professional activity; 3) development of abilities and skills to perform research tasks, to select adequate goals and methods of research and data processing; 4) ability to discuss research results; 5) ability to self-analyze and self-assess the level of research competence development.

The methodological component includes principles (unity of scientific and educational activity, professional orientation, unity of theoretical and practical activity, consideration of personal capabilities) and scientific approaches (personally oriented, competence-based, activity-based, systemic).

The content-procedural component singles out the pedagogical conditions, structural components and stages of research competence development, as well as the ways of their implementation using various forms, means and methods.

The diagnostic-corrective component includes diagnosis of the research competence development levels, analysis and evaluation of the results, detection of the academic staff satisfaction degree with the joint creative activity. This component also implies the development of criteria and indicators; use of evaluation methods for each criterion; analysis of the results achieved. The definition of levels (reproductive, constructive, creative) for each criterion (motivational-developmental, cognitive-directed, activity-practical, re-

flective-corrective) involves the development of a diagnostic support system, which includes questionnaires, testing, observation, expert evaluation methods, self-evaluation methods and identification of orientation towards research activity.

During the implementation of the above-mentioned model, the following interactive methods were used: communicative role-playing game, brainstorming, heuristic questions, research, case method, reflection, etc.

The main activities were: individual, pair, group; lecture-visualization; training exercises, independent and practical tasks; participation in scientific and practical conferences, workshops, discussion groups; internship.

Among the means of the research competence development model implementation for the academic staff were: access to information databases; modern scientific research, multimedia equipment, interactive whiteboard, Internet, computers, etc.

Having analyzed the results of scientific and pedagogical research, in accordance with the principles of phasing and sequence, we suggest to distinguish the following stages of the research competence development: generalizing (selection of topics for research work according to research directions, literature review); operational (conducting independent scientific research that is of a practical value; internship in operational units); analytical (data analysis, generalization, theorizing, description and explanation of facts, substantiation of regularities, selection of correlational and cause-and-effect relationships, which result is the description and explanation of the studied phenomenon, object, process); synthetic (conducting extended scientific research, preparing articles based on research results, writing a paper; developing methodical recommendations); integration (the process of thesis defense); research (generating new ideas in research and scientific-professional activities).

Therefore, the process of diagnosing the research competence development of the academic staff can be divided into the following stages:

1. Organizational (identification of the issue that needs to be studied; elaboration of methodological recommendations for the definition and research competence development in the professional activity of the academic staff; creation of relevant lectures etc).

2. Design and prognostic (diagnosis and evaluation of the existing state of research competence and working out the technology for its development).

3. Epistemological (visiting relevant classes and trainings in order to improve the awareness of research skills; formation of theoretical knowledge of research competence development).

4. Innovative-technological (acquiring skills in the practical use of modern educational technologies, creating one's own databases with the classification of acquired materials).

5. Reflective and corrective (assessment, self-assessment, analysis of the research competence level achieved, determination of corrective measures, recommendations for further development in the process of independent professional research activity).

Therefore, the research competence development

model of the academic staff in terms of the educational and scientific process includes a wide range of structural components, which are interconnected and reveal the internal organization of the academic staff development process: the goal, tasks, principles and scientific approaches of implementation, procedural blocks (target, methodological, content-procedural, diagnostic-corrective), pedagogical conditions and stages of research competence development and diagnostic result.

The quality of the suggested model for the academic staff is reflected in:

- openness to innovative changes;
- positive attitude towards self-development and "lifelong learning";
- use of new technologies, expansion of the information space;
- improvement of scientific and methodical support;
- ability to foresee the results of their activities, to model them on the basis of modern scientific and practical achievements.

Thus, the above-mentioned model of the research competence development of the academic staff in higher educational institutions reflects the educational and scientific process under the specified pedagogical conditions and stages of the research competence development, which can become the basis for determining the goals, content, forms and methods of improving both professional and pedagogical progress.

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